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Application template

Small-Scale Initiatives in
Machine Learning
(OpenSSI 2022c)

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Small-Scale Initiatives in Machine Learning (OpenSSI 2022c)

Title:	<i>Project title</i>
Acronym or abbreviation:	<i>Project acronym or abbreviation</i>
Lead applicant (LA):	<i>Title and name of LA</i>
PhD:	<i>Date on which PhD was obtained</i>
Position and affiliation LA:	<i>To determine the eligibility of LA</i>
Email address LA:	<i>For e-mail communication with LA</i>
Postal address LA:	<i>For postal correspondence with LA</i>
Start date:	<i>Estimated date for starting the project, not before 1 January 2023</i>
End date:	<i>Estimated end date of project, not later than 31 December 2024. (Exact dates will be determined in consultation with the eScience Center once the project is awarded)</i>
Requested RSE support	<i>768 hours (0.5 FTE, 6 Person months) (fixed)</i>
Domain:	<i>Choose one of the following</i>

- Life Sciences**, incl. biology, medical and health sciences, neuroscience;
- Physical Sciences and Engineering**, incl. agricultural sciences, astrophysics, chemistry, computer science, earth sciences, engineering, environmental sciences, mathematics, physics;
- Social Sciences and Humanities**, incl. anthropology, archaeology, communication studies, economics, education sciences, history, human geography, law, linguistics, literary studies, philosophy, political sciences, psychology, sociology.

Summary for the eScience Center website (max. 150 words)

Please provide a non-expert summary of the proposal for use on the eScience Center website and other media. This summary will be made public only in case the proposal is awarded. The eScience Center reserves the right to edit the text for reasons of consistency, correctness, formatting or otherwise.

Research team

	Name	E-mail	Position & Affiliation	ORCID (if available)	Contribution to the team	Availability for this project (hours/week)
Lead applicant						
Research team member 1						
Research team member 2						
Research team member 3						
Research team member 4						

If applicable, for each piece of software and/or dataset:

Name:	<i>Name of the software or dataset</i>
License:	<i>License, if any (e.g. Apache 2 or GPL)</i>
Location:	<i>URL where the software of dataset can be downloaded for inspection</i>
Documentation:	<i>URL(s) with documentation, if any</i>

Research Question (max. 250 words)

Describe the research problem you are planning to work on and pose a concise research question following from that problem. Provide context for the importance of the problem being solved. Please describe:

- the project's objectives and use case
- the research problem, the research question and scientific approach
- the expected impact of the software on the research community
- the expected output (papers, blog posts, code release, etc).

Digital Solutions (max. 400 words)

Describe the advantages of the machine learning solution you envision in relation to the current state of the art in your domain, with regard to your research topic.

- what is the current digital technology of choice? What are its limitations?
- how can machine learning methods contribute to solving the research problem?
- describe what the machine learning solution should do

Research sustainability (max. 250 words)

Describe your plans for the continuation of the envisaged research after completion of the project, including the software resulting from collaboration with eScience Center RSEs.

- how will the proposed research be continued after completion of the project (additional funding opportunities)?
- how and who will maintain the software and/ or dataset after completion of the project?
- how will you attract new users and integrate the software into a larger research community?

Statement by the applicant

The Netherlands eScience Center strictly applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU (see www.eugdpr.org). In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must strictly apply these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

The eScience Center endorses the Code Openness Animal Experiments and the Biosecurity Code of Conduct (available at www.knaw.nl). Applicants must check whether the codes have relevance to their application. If so, the eScience Center requires applicants to endorse the code(s) and act according to these. In case of the Biosecurity Code the applicant is convinced that the knowledge presented in the application cannot lead to dual use.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

- I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the ‘Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG), as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- I endorse and follow the Code Openness Animal Experiments (if applicable).
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP. **If ‘NO’, then please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the proposal.**
- I have informed my employing institute of the submission of this proposal, by sending a copy of the application to the formally mandated representative of my research organization (e.g. director, head of department, dean).
- I have completed this form truthfully.

Name (LA):

Place:

Date: